

A STUDY ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF ALUMINA BORATE WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

W. D. Fei, L. J. Yao, and C. K. Yao

*School of Materials Science and Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin 150001, P. R. China*

SUMMARY: The squeeze casting method was used to fabricate alumina borate whisker reinforced aluminum composite with the whisker volume fraction of 25%, the matrix alloy is Al-Si-Mg alloy (AC8A alloy). The microstructure of the composite was studied Using TEM observation. The results indicated that the feature of the microstructure of the composite can be described as follows: the first one is that the interfacial reaction exists between the whisker and Al-Si-Mg alloy; the second one is that twins and dislocations were found in the whisker; the third one is that higher densified dislocation exists in the matrix of the composite. The twin and dislocation in the whisker were considered as the results of relaxation of residual stress due to the thermal mismatch between the whisker and aluminum alloy.

KEYWORDS: alumina borate whisker, aluminum matrix composite, microstructure, twin, dislocation, thermal mismatch, residual stress, stress relaxation

INTRODUCTION

Because of higher properties and formability, aluminum matrix composites reinforced by whisker were widely studied, it is very important to reduce the cost for large scale application of this kind of materials. Sukanuma et al [1] and the Hu et al [2] showed that the properties of alumina borate whisker ($\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$) reinforced aluminum composite exhibits excellent properties and low cost, so the composite was received more interesting.

Although many studies were about the microstructure and properties of alumina borate whisker reinforced aluminum composite[1-4], few studies were concerning the evolution mechanism of the microstructure of composite, especially the defect in the whisker. As well known, the microstructure plays a key role on the properties of composites, it is very important to understand and control the microstructure for the optimization of composite properties. In the present research, the microstructures both in the matrix and whisker was investigated by TEM observation, and the formation mechanism of the microstructure in the composite was discussed in detail.

EXPERIMENTS

The $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker reinforced AC8A alumni alloy composite was fabricated by squeeze casting method, and the volume fraction of the whisker is 25%, the composition of AC8A alloy is Si: 11.0mass%, Mg: 1.0mass%, Cu: 0.8mass%, Ni: 1.0mass%, 87.2mass%. The casting temperature is 800°C , and the temperature of the mold is about 450°C .

The specimens for TEM observation is prepared by ion milling manhood. The TEM observation was carried out in a CM-12 type transmission electron microscope with the operation voltage of 120kV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The TEM micrograph of the interface $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /AC8A composite was shown in Fig.1, it is clear that an obvious interfacial reaction exists between the whisker and the AC8A alloy, we had identified that the interfacial reaction product is MgAl_2O_4 with spinal structure and shown that the interfacial reaction can affect the composite properties greatly[2-4].

*Fig.1: TEM photos of the interface of $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /AC8A composite
(a) micrograph, (b) SADP*

Fig. 2 is the TEM micrograph of $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /AC8A composite, dislocation and pile-up of dislocation can be found in the whisker and the dislocations are not straight, which means that the dislocations are movable in the whisker. The presence of movable dislocation suggested that the whisker can be deformed by dislocation motion. The stress which lead to the dislocation motion in the whisker may be the relaxation of thermal residual stress in the composite.

As the great difference of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the whisker and matrix alloy, the residual stress must be induced into the composite when the composite was cooled down from fabrication temperature. The thermal residual stress may be so high that the dislocation in the whisker can be moved by it.

Fig.2: Dislocation in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}/AC8A$ composite

Fig. 3 is the twin in the $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker, from Fig. 3, it can be seen that the twin plan is parallel to the longitudinal direction of whisker. Because the main growth direction of the whisker is the longitudinal direction, the twin shown in Fig. 3 is deformation twin, not growth twin. The formation of deformation twin in the whisker is due to the relaxation of thermal residual stress in the whisker as discussed above.

Fig. 3: Twin in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}/AC8A$ composite

TEM observation (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) show that $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker can be deformed by dislocation motion and deformation twin. The results is very interesting, the residual stress in the composite can be relaxed by whisker deformation, on the other hand the dislocation motion and deformation twin formation may affect the deformation mechanism of the composite, which need to be studied further.

Because of Si content of Si in AC8A alloy is higher, the phases in the matrix of the composite are aluminum and silicon. TEM micrographs of matrix in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}/Al$ composite are shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4(a), the high density of dislocation can be seen in aluminum phase of the matrix; and the deformation twin in silicon phase of the matrix can be found. High density of defects in the matrix suggests that the matrix was deformed greatly. It is clear that the driving force for the matrix deformation is the same for the deformation of whisker, i.e. the residual stress in the composite is very high, which can be higher than the yield strength of the composite. Comparing the density of defects in the matrix with that in the whisker, it can be found that the density in the matrix is much higher than that in the whisker, which is due to the yield strength of the matrix being much lower than that of the whisker, plastic deformation must be higher in the matrix than that in the whisker at the same residual stress.

Fig. 4: TEM micrographs of the matrix in $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}/Al$ composite
(a) Al phase, (b) Si phase

The residual stress in metal matrix composite is almost avoided, which can influence many properties of the composite. From the present study, one can find that the residual stress can be relaxed by two ways: one is plastic deformation of the whisker, another is plastic deformation of the matrix. Because the difference of CTE between the whisker and aluminum alloy is quite high, when the composite was cooled down from fabrication temperature, the residual stress must be induced into the composite, and the residual stress is higher than the yield strength of the composite, so the plastic deformation takes place.

The plastic deformation of the whisker and matrix may take place at various temperatures during the cooling process of the composite, because of the residual stress in the composite may be very high, the deformation of the composite due to relaxation of the residual stress may be a continuous process. The high density of dislocations in the matrix can enhance the strength of the matrix or the composite. The residual stress can be relaxed both in the matrix and whisker, which can reduce the residual stress level in the composite, which may be beneficial to the shape stability of the composite parts, in the point of view, to study this effect is important for some applications of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

Interfacial reaction exists between the $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker and AC8A alloy.

Dislocation and deformation twin were observed in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{AC8A}$ composite, the formation of the defects is due to the relaxation of residual stress in the composite.

High densified dislocation exists in Al phase and deformation twin in Si phase in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{AC8A}$ composite, which also results from the relaxation of residual stress in the composite

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